

TECHNIQUES FOR CHARACTERIZING ELBOW AND SHOULDER MECHANICS AND NEURAL CONTROL IN NORMAL AND DISABLED SUBJECTS

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes a robotic manipulator and several analysis techniques which have been devised to characterize human arm biomechanics and to investigate the neural control of arm posture and movement. The importance of limb stiffness in understanding normal neural control strategies and in restoring arm function to individuals with quadriplegia resulting from spinal cord injury is discussed. The manipulator has the capacity to impose constant loads of greater than 225 N and to impose stochastic force perturbations with a bandwidth of 50 Hz. A modification of a standard single input-single output system identification technique to identify endpoint stiffness properties is discussed. The use of these experimental and analytical techniques to study whole arm posture and movement, shoulder joint posture and internal joint stability, and arm control in quadriplegic subjects is described.

INTRODUCTION

The arm is used in most activities of daily living, and the neural control of arm posture and movement has been widely studied. Many of these studies have examined the isolated function of single joints (e.g., [5]), but an increasing number have begun examining multi-joint arm tasks [3,6], as the importance of inter-joint inertial coupling, multi-articular muscles, and skeletal geometry have become apparent. In particular, the kinematics of unconstrained, horizontal plane arm movements have been widely studied.

Although kinematics are useful for examining movement performance, many arm-related tasks involve interactions with the external environment, including both predictable loads and unexpected perturbations. Under these conditions, limb stiffness (the relationship between an imposed displacement and the evoked force or moment) is central to the control of the arm because this is the property which determines the stability of a posture or movement trajectory in the face of internal or external disturbances. Because stiffness arises from the coordinated activity of the musculature of the limb, its characterization provides insight into neural control strategies for multi-joint arm movements. An understanding of appropriate limb stiffness properties is also essential for facilitating the development of rehabilitation approaches for individuals with central nervous system lesions or traumatic injury. Although normal neural control mechanisms may be quite different than neuroprostheses utilizing functional neuromuscular stimulation to restore arm function to individuals with quadriplegia resulting from spinal cord injury, the basic stability and movement performance requirements (summarized by stiffness properties) are similar.

The stiffness of a multi-joint limb is a directional quantity [3,5] whose characterization requires a device capable of

imposing forces or displacements of adequate amplitude in at least two orthogonal directions. The complexity of these devices has limited the number of studies which have examined multi-joint stiffness properties and the conditions under which it has been measured. This report will describe a manipulator which has been designed and built in our laboratory to allow measurement of arm stiffness under a wide range of conditions, as well as several ongoing and future projects which will use this device.

Figure 1: Manipulator mechanical design
MANIPULATOR PERFORMANCE

The manipulator used in our laboratory was designed to perform two basic functions: (1) to generate controlled loads against which subjects must maintain a posture or produce a movement, and (2) to impose perturbations on the endpoint of the limb for stiffness estimation and to evoke reflex responses. The ability of the manipulator to perform these functions will be documented in the following sections.

Figure 2: Maximum force capacity

Basic mechanics. Figure 1 is a schematic representation of the basic mechanical structure of the manipulator. It consists of two lightweight arm segments driven via a steel cable transmission by two DC torque motors. The arm and motors are supported on a structure which allows the plane of action to be vertically translated over a wide range and also to be inclined over a range of approximately 130°. The arm has a planar workspace sufficient to incorporate a large class of arm movements. Substantial forces can be developed at the endpoint of the manipulator arm; Figure 2 illustrates the force output of the manipulator when driven with a rotating, near-maximal input command, indicating that at least 225 N can be produced in any planar direction.

Instrumentation and control. Potentiometers attached to each manipulator joint sense the two joint angles and a JR3 6-axis force transducer (JR3, Inc.) is attached to the endpoint of the arm at the interface of the manipulator and the arm of the subject. Tachometers internal to the motors provide velocity signals. The potentiometer and velocity signals, as well as the two force components in the plane of manipulator movement are sampled by a digital signal processing (DSP) board (Spectrum, Inc.) and used to control either endpoint force or endpoint position (in this plane). A combination feedback/feedforward endpoint force control strategy [1,4] has been implemented in each Cartesian direction, while position control has been implemented at the joint angle level using standard proportional-derivative controllers. Each control algorithm is implemented on the DSP in assembly language and runs at a bandwidth of 1 kHz or higher.

Figure 3: Stochastic force perturbations

Figure 3 illustrates the production of endpoint force perturbations (in both directions in the plane) of the type to be used in several experimental paradigms. The magnitude of the perturbation is adequate to produce a small displacement of the limb without significantly disrupting the task performed (posture or movement); the illustrated bandwidth of approximately 50 Hz indicates the capability of the manipulator but is significantly wider than the 15 - 20 Hz bandwidth that will be used in most paradigms.

EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN AND ANALYSIS

Although different studies will utilize somewhat different experimental paradigms, the basic approach in most will be similar and will be described in the following paragraphs.

Stochastic perturbations. The endpoint stiffness of the arm (shoulder and elbow) has been studied previously using "step" displacements imposed on the hand [6]. Because of the directional character of endpoint stiffness, this requires a time-consuming experimental procedure of 16 or more perturbation directions, and stiffness estimates also rely upon subjects suppressing all voluntary reactions to the displacement. We have instead decided to use stochastic endpoint perturbations because their unpredictability reduces voluntary reactions to a minimum and because endpoint stiffness can be characterized in a single trial. Both endpoint force and endpoint displacement perturbations will be used in different paradigms.

System identification. The use of stochastic endpoint perturbations also has the advantage that efficient system

identification procedures [2,5] can be used to characterize the stiffness dynamics of the arm. These techniques have been previously used for single joint systems [5], but have now been extended to identify the four components of the planar endpoint stiffness of the arm. The 4 components arise because a perturbation in *either* one of the planar directions evokes responses in *both* directions. The two force components in the plane of manipulator action are obtained from the JR3 transducer, while endpoint position (as well as shoulder and elbow joint angles) are recorded using an OptoTrak (Northern Digital, Inc.) motion analysis system. For postural conditions, a linear, single-input, single-output identification procedure [2] is applied 4 separate times (using the different combinations of 2 force inputs and 2 output displacements) to identify the 4 endpoint stiffness components. The endpoint stiffness matrix can then be transformed into joint stiffnesses to facilitate interpretation. Arm movements will be examined using a modified form of a time-varying identification procedure [5] that will allow characterization of endpoint stiffness modulation during such nonstationary conditions.

APPLICATIONS

The apparatus and techniques described above will be used to examine several aspects of the control of arm posture and movement. In normal subjects, the effects of external load and limb geometry on the endpoint stiffness properties of the arm and on reflex EMG responses will be characterized. Substantial loads will also be imposed on the limb to investigate the control of shoulder joint internal stability, most of which is mediated by muscle action rather than by skeletal elements. Similar techniques will be used to evaluate the performance of cervical spinal cord injury patients who have had tendon transfer surgery to restore voluntary control of elbow extension or wrist extension, or who have been implemented with a functional neuromuscular stimulation system for restoring forearm pronation and elbow extension functions.

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REFERENCES

- [1] C.H. An, C.G. Atkeson, and J.M. Hollerbach, *Model-Based Control of a Robot Manipulator*, MIT Press, 1988.
- [2] I.W. Hunter and R.E. Kearney, "Two-sided linear filter identification", *Med. Biol. Eng. Comput.* 21:203-209, 1983.
- [3] N. Hogan, "The mechanics of multi-joint posture and movement control", *Biol. Cybern.*, 52: 315-331, 1985.
- [4] B.C. Kuo, *Digital Control Systems*, 2nd ed. Saunders College Publishing, 1992.
- [5] J.B. MacNeil, R.E. Kearney, and I.W. Hunter, "Identification of time-varying biological systems from ensemble data", *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.* 39: 1213-1225, 1992.
- [6] F.A. Mussa-Ivaldi, N. Hogan, and E. Bizzi, "Neural, mechanical, and geometric factors subserving arm posture in humans", *J. Neurosci.*, 5: 2732-2743, 1985.